

Systematic Technology Review of OGC Standards and OSGeo Projects

Luiz Fernando Satolo¹, Lúbia Vinhas²

¹ INPE, Av. Dos Astronautas 1758, 12227-010 – São José dos Campos, SP – Brazil – satololuiz@gmail.com

² INPE, Av. Dos Astronautas 1758, 12227-010 – São José dos Campos, SP – Brazil – lubia.vinhas@inpe.br

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Abstract

OGC Standards and OSGeo Projects have been widely applied to different kinds of geospatial data and extended for the implementation of geospatial data science environments. However, there's no review comprehensively summarizing and discussing the progress of these open source technologies for publishing geospatial databases on the Web. The proposed Systematic Technology Review is a stylized version of the Systematic Literature Review, covering the documentation of OGC Standards and OSGeo Projects. To recognize the main topics of each technology in detail, the documentation was analyzed by Latent Dirichlet Allocation using Python. The adoption of the technologies were evaluated based on the number of Github forks and stars, as well as Docker pulls. The latest developments in terms of the OGC Standards for data encoding took place in the GeoPackage. For accessing, processing or visualizing data, the trend was the development of OGC API related standards. However, GML is the OGC Standard for data encoding most implemented in OSGeo Projects, along with Web Services like WMS, WFS, WCS and WPS for accessing, processing and visualizing. The Latent Dirichlet Allocation analyses found eight topics underlying the OGC Standard and OSGeo projects. The keywords of the top four topics were conformance, layer, tile and response.

1.0 Introduction

Geospatial data are portions of information collected using technologies such as GPS, radio-frequency identifications, volunteered geographic information and location-based social networks (Al-Yadumi et al., 2021). Since the mid 1990s, the development of digital map libraries, spatial data warehouses and geoportals had a dramatic impact on the availability of digital geospatial data (Dangermond and Goodchild, 2020).

To support the ability of applications to exchange geospatial data, a series of standards and protocols for publishing geospatial databases on the Web has been developed. Among them, the Open Geospatial Consortium - OGC Standards define interoperable approaches to Data Encoding, Data Access, Data Processing, Data Visualization, and Metadata and Catalogue Services. Based on the FAIR principles, the OGC Standards provide a free, open and stable basis for the development of geospatial solutions (OGC, 2024).

While OGC is an organization for creating geospatial standards, the Open Source Geospatial - OSGeo is an organization for promoting open source geospatial software and data. The foundation provides financial, organizational and legal support to the broader open source geospatial community. It is also an explicit goal of OSGeo to support and promote standards, including OGC standards. The foundation's projects have undergone an extensive mentorship program with the organization and are all freely available under a certified open source license (OSGeo, 2024).

Following the paradigm of Systematic Reviews (Pati and Lorusso, 2018), this paper presents a Systematic Technology Review of OGC Standards and OSGeo Projects. The purpose of this review is to analyze the progress of open source technologies for publishing geospatial databases on the Web and to make recommendations for future developments.

2.0 Methodology

The proposed Systematic Technology Review is a stylized version of the Systematic Literature Review, covering the documentation of OGC Standards and OSGeo Projects. This review adapted the methodology presented in Tranfield et al. (2003), and it's comprised of the Stages and Phases listed in Table 1. In order to produce a systematic, explicit, comprehensive and reproducible review of the aforementioned technologies, this paper followed the steps proposed in Okoli and Schabram (2015) and, where applicable, it also adopted the resources of PRISMA-P (Shamseer et al., 2015).

Stage	Phase
I - Planning the review	0 - Identification of the need for a review 1 - Preparation of a proposal for review 2 - Development of a review protocol
II - Conducting the review	3 - Identification of the technology 4 - Selection of documentation 5 - Documentation quality assessment 6 - Data extraction and monitoring progress 7 - Data synthesis
III - Reporting and dissemination	8 - The report and recommendations 9 - Getting evidence into practice

Table 1. Systematic Technology Review methodology.
Source: based on Tranfield et al. (2003).

The decision to restrict the review to the standards specified by OGC is justified by the fact that they are "developed through consensus, and backed by government and organizations across the globe" (OGC, 2024). Regarding to open source geospatial software, the review is restricted to OSGeo projects because, similarly, they are result of community driven developments (OSGeo, 2024).

Instead of querying for keywords in databases, the search strategy consisted of screening OGC and OSGeo websites for

Figure 2. OGC Standards history.
The yellow stars indicate the OGC Standards that are equivalent to ISO Standards.

Topic	Keyword	OGC standards	OSGeo projects	Total
1	response	17	0	17
2	option	1	4	5
3	raster	3	4	7
4	image	2	1	3
5	conformance	28	0	28
6	layer	2	20	22
7	tile	19	1	20
8	annotation	5	0	5

Table 3. Number of technologies by keyword.

Based on the analysis of the Implementation Specification and Community Standard documentations, the most similar OGC Standards were OGC API - Tiles (OGC API - Tiles Development Team, 2022) and Two Dimensional Tile Matrix Set (Two Dimensional Tile Matrix Set Development Team, 2022). On the other hand, based on the analysis of manuals, the most similar OSGeo Projects were GDAL (GDAL Development Team, 2024) and MDAL (MDAL Development Team, 2021).

The strongest relationship between an OGC Standard and an OSGeo Project occurred between WPS (WPS Development Team, 2018) and ZOO-project (ZOO-project Development Team, 2019), followed by WPS (WPS Development Team, 2018) and PyWPS (PyWPS Development Team, 2018). Overall, the OSGeo Project most closely related to the entire set of OGC Standards was rasdaman (rasdaman Development Team, 2023), followed by MapServer (MapServer Development Team, 2023) and deegree (deegree Development Team, 2024).

Notably, a large group of standards and projects showed scarce connections (Figure 3), mainly those that are domain-specific, like PubSub (PubSub Development Team, 2016), LAS (LAS Development Team, 2018), and PipelineML (PipelineML Development Team, 2019) among the OGC Standards and like Giswater (Giswater Development Team, 2022) and MobilityDB (MobilityDB Development Team, 2022) among the OSGeo Community Projects, or those that are the basis of the other technologies, like Simple Features (Simple Features Development Team, 2011), WKT (WKT Development Team, 2023) and Coordinate Transformation (Coordinate Transformation Development Team, 2001) standards and like PROJ (PROJ Development Team, 2024) and PostGIS (PostGIS Development Team, 2024) projects.

4.0 Conclusion

The presented Systematic Technology Review can promote the evolution of the current OGC Standards and OSGeo Projects, as well as the development of new technologies. It can also support developers of new solutions in the geospatial community. Specifically, this review is the basis for the proposal of a new library to promote integrated access to INPE's environmental databases. An important limitation of this systematic review is that it was not possible to find any PDF documentation for almost 20% of the existing technologies, which were excluded from the analysis.

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Figure 3. Network of similarities between OGC Standards and OSGeo projects.

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Appendix

id	Standard	Type	Latest	Reviewed	Included
0	2D Tile Matrix Set	IS	2.0.0	2.0.0	✓
1	3D Tiles	CS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
2	3dP	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
3	ARML2.0	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
4	Cat2.0ebRIM	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
5	Catalogue Services	IS	3.0.0	3.0.0	✓
6	CDB	IS	1.2.0	1.2.0	✓
7	CityGML	IS	3.0.0	3.0.0	✓
8	CityJSON	CS	2.0.0	2.0.0	✓
9	COG	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
10	Coordinate Transformation	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
11	CoverageJSON	CS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
12	EO-GeoJSON	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
13	Filter Encoding	IS	2.0.3	2.0.0	✓
14	GeoAPI	IS	3.0.1	3.0.0	✓
15	GeoPackage	IS	1.4.0	1.4.0	✓
16	GeoPose	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
17	GeoSciML	IS	4.1.0	4.1.0	✓
18	GeoSPARQL	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
19	GeoRSS	CS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
20	GeoTIFF	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
21	GeoXACML	IS	3.0.0	3.0.0	✓
22	GML	IS	3.3.0	3.3.0	✓
23	GMLJP2	IS	2.1.0	2.1.0	✓
24	GUF	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
25	GWML2	IS	2.2.1	2.2.1	✓
26	HDF5	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
27	I3S	CS	1.3.0	1.3.0	✓
28	IMDF	CS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
29	IndoorGML	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
30	KML	IS	2.3.0	2.3.0	✓
31	LandInfra / InfraGML	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
32	LAS	CS	1.4.0	1.4.0	✓
33	Moving Features	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
34	NetCDF	IS	3.1.0	3.1.0	✓
35	OGC API - Common	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
36	OGC API - EDR	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
37	OGC API - Features	IS	1.0.1	1.0.1	✓
38	OGC API - Processes	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
39	OGC API - Tiles	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
40	OMS	IS	2.0.0	2.0.0	✓
41	Open GeoSMS	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
42	OpenLS	IS	1.2.0	1.2.0	✓
43	OpenMI	IS	2.0.0	2.0.0	✓
44	OpenSearch	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
45	Ordering Services for EO	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
46	OWS Context	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
47	OWS Security	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
48	PipelineML	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
49	PubSub	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
50	PUCK	IS	1.4.0	1.4.0	✓
	Semantic Sensor Network	O			✗
51	Sensor Observation Service	IS	2.0.0	2.0.0	✓
52	Sensor Planning Service	IS	2.0.0	2.0.0	✓
53	SensorML	IS	2.1.0	2.1.0	✓
54	SensorThings	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
55	STApplus	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
56	Simple Features	IS	1.2.1	1.2.1	✓
57	Simple Features CORBA	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
58	Simple Features OLE/COM	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
59	Simple Features SQL	IS	1.2.1	1.2.1	✓

60	Styled Layer Descriptor	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
	Symbology Core	CM			✗
61	Symbology Encoding	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
62	SWE Common Data Model	IS	2.0.0	2.0.0	✓
63	SWE Service Model	IS	2.0.0	2.0.0	✓
64	Table Joining Service	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
	Time Ontology	O			✗
65	TimeSeriesML	IS	1.3.0	1.3.0	✓
66	TrainingDML-AI	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
67	WaterML	IS	2.2.0	2.2.0	✓
68	WCPS	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
69	WCS	IS	2.1.0	2.1.0	✓
70	Web Map Context	IS	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
71	Web Service Common	IS	2.0.0	2.0.0	✓
72	WFS	IS	2.0.2	2.0.2	✓
73	WKT CRS	IS	2.1.11	2.1.11	✓
74	WMS	IS	1.3.0	1.3.0	✓
75	WMTS	IS	1.0.0	1.0.0	✓
76	WPS	IS	2.0.2	2.0.2	✓

Table A1 - OGC Standards
Source: based on OGC (2024).

id	Project	Type	Latest	Reviewed	Included
	actinia	CP	4.13.1	-	✗
77	deegree webservice	OP	3.5.7	3.5.7	✓
	ETF	CP	1.0.0	-	✗
78	FDO	CP	4.0.0	3.2.0	✓
	GC2/Vidi	CP	2024.5.2	-	✗
79	GDAL/OGR	OP	3.9.0	3.9.0	✓
	GeoExt	CP	6.0.0	-	✗
80	GeoHealthCheck	CP	0.9.0	0.9.0	✓
81	GeoMoose	OP	3.x	2.9.3	✓
82	GeoNetwork	OP	4.4.0	2.10.4	✓
83	GeoNode	OP	4.2.4	3.2.0	✓
	GEOS	OP	3.13.0dev	-	✗
84	GeoServer	OP	2.25.0	2.16.1	✓
	Geoserver Client PHP	CP	0.4.1	-	✗
	GeoStyler	CP	14.1.2	-	✗
	GeoTools	OP	31.0	-	✗
	GeoWebCache	CP	1.26.0	-	✗
85	Giswater	CP	3.6.0	3.6.0	✓
	GRASS GIS	OP	8.3	-	✗
86	gvSIG Desktop	OP	2.4.0	2.3.0	✓
	istSOS	CP	2.4.0	-	✗
	Loader	CP	1.3.0	-	✗
	Marble	OP	2.2.0	-	✗
87	Mapbender	OP	3.3.0	3.3.0	✓
88	mapfish	CP	3.30.6	2.0.0	✓
89	MapGuide	CP	3.1.2	1.2.0	✓
	mappyfile	CP	1.0.0	-	✗
90	MapServer	OP	8.0.1	8.0.1	✓
91	MDAL	CP	1.1.0	1.1.0	✓
92	MobilityDB	CP	1.1.1	1.0.0	✓
93	Open Data Cube	CP	1.8.18	1.0.4	✓
94	OpenLayers	OP	8.1.0	2.13.0	✓
	Opticks	CP	4.11.0-rc1	-	✗
95	OSSIM	CP	1.8.20	1.6.5	✓
	OSGeo4W	S			✗
	OSGeoLive	S			✗
96	Orfeo ToolBox	OP	9.0.0	6.4.0	✓
	OWSLib	CP	0.32.dev0	-	✗
97	pgRouting	CP	3.6.2	2.6.0	✓
98	Portable GIS	CP	5.6.8	5.6.8	✓

99	PostGIS	OP	3.5.0dev	3.5.0dev	✓	104	QGIS Desktop	OP	3.34	3.34	✓
100	PROJ	OP	9.5.0-dev	9.4.0	✓	105	rasdaman	CP	10.3.0	10.1.0	✓
	PROJ-JNI	CP	2.0.0	-	✗		TEAM Engine	CP	6.0.0-RC1	-	✗
	Pronto Raster	CP	0.3	-	✗		TorchGeo	CP	0.6.0dev	-	✗
101	pycsw	OP	3.0-dev	2.6.1	✓	106	ZOO-project	OP	2.0.0-rc2	1.8.0	✓
102	pygeoapi	OP	0.17.dev0	0.13.0	✓						
103	PyWPS	OP	4.3.dev0	4.3.dev0	✓						

Table A2 - OSGeo Projects

Source: based on OSGeo (2024).